

Intermolecular Forces in a Physical Molecular Visualization System: A Human-Computer Interaction Application

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ABSTRACT:

This paper extends the concept of self-reconfigurable physical programming to incorporate attraction and repulsion forces between physical objects controlled by a software, Unity 3D engine. Those forces are further explained as force curves that justify the behavior of molecules under specific circumstances. A better programming methodology for physical structures is represented in this paper for demonstrating an interactive 3D physical simulation of the attraction and repulsion forces. The bottom-up programming of self-reconfigurable mid-air flying drones has proved to be more efficient in facilitating code modifications, maintenance, and scalability. The implementation evaluation covered drones' response latency and accuracy as a drones' deviation ratio from the correct path. The evaluation results show marginal latency measures and considerably high accuracy in the drones' movements. This opens the door for many future works on this subject to improve its scalability and adaptability in similar self-reconfigurable physical structures programming projects.

Keywords: Human-Computer Interaction, Programmable Matter, Intermolecular Interaction, Intermolecular Force Curves.

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INTRODUCTION

Programmable Matter (PM) was first introduced by Toffoli and Margolus in 1991 [1]; the idea is to program multiple small physical particles to perform a significant coordinated task. PM is a mechanism that helps to integrate disconnected units of multipurpose computing devices to accomplish a particular demonstration [1].

Programmable Matter, or physical programming, is based upon the natural relationship between particles of forms of matter and their behavior under specific circumstances (e.g., heating, freezing) [2].

Virtual reality lacks a true physical presence. But PM has the advantage over virtual reality of providing a more interactive and physical communication style between users and the programmable structures [3, 4]. This ability of direct communication and interaction with physical structures proved through experiments to enhance comprehension, proportional to the level of interaction that a user is able to practice with the physical structures.

In the following section we discuss PM, self-reconfiguration, control mechanisms, force curves, and 3D physical visualization. Then, the current paper's contribution will be described. Following that is a discussion of the experiment implementation details and utilized tools.

RELATED WORK

Programmable Matter

PM is viewed as one useful outcome of assembling millimeter-scale units. These computable miniature units have the ability to apply shaping algorithms in a high-volume nanoscale level [3, 5].

A “claytronic” is an industrialized form of programmable matter developed by Goldstein and Mowry [6]. Claytronics use an ensemble of coordinated modular robots to combine audio and video in Pario, a media type used to construct 3D objects in a highly scaled manner [6].

programmable matter was extended via introducing 3D interactive displays called BitDrones [7]. BitDrones are physical blocks that can self-levitate with the ability to self-reshape in three dimensions. 3D BitDrones’ ability of self-reconfiguration helps to mimic physical movements without the use of external control tools [7].

BitDrones were later extended to PixelDrones, ShapeDrones, and DisplayDrones [2, 3]. But what makes BitDrones exceptional is their ability to represent physical 3D data interactively, by means of nanoquadcopters [8].

Self-Reconfiguration

Self-reconfigurable materials are those “that can change form and appearance dynamically” [9] and independently. Self-reconfiguration is the ability of the individual physical components to move relative to each other, by means of repulsing and attracting forces. These movements due to attraction and repulsion can be used to carry out automated shape transformations.

Poupyrev discussed the idea of self-reconfiguration in terms of self-reshapeable output displays [10]. Robots with embedded visual images (called “Displays”) were first introduced in 2004 as “Lumen” [10, 11, 12]. Each output display consists of an LCD screen structure. Display self-reshaping is accomplished by first sensing the self-shape, then sensing the current forces applied on those displays. Display self-reshaping limits the rigidity of usual screens planar structures [12].

Kurokawa *et al.* ran an experiment on intelligent and systemized robots to form a 3D construct that can self-reconfigure. These intelligent robots can configure their neighboring structures, then relocate them through an arm rotation mechanism until they reach the assigned 3D configuration [13].

Schneegass *et al.* argued that, in the coming few years, self-reconfiguring robots and free-floating displays will contribute to the public service. Researchers have also speculated that those type of displays could replace any kind of surface [14].

Scheible *et al.* showed the utility of intelligent robots in the public service through their systematic experiments on flying robots. This research used intelligent robots as interactive flying displays, by augmenting them with video projectors [15]. The flying projectors could successfully project onto different surfaces in public due to their projection orientation accuracy, their speed, and their flexibility.

Control Mechanisms

There are many ways to control the self-reconfiguration process. Control software systems are more than just kinematics computations programmed algorithmically in robust systems. In fact, they involve visual trackers, sensors, operators, energy, and internal/external communication mechanisms [16]. Such distributed controllers can guarantee an optimal multi-robotic deployment that is independent yet adapts collision free curves and fast conjunctions [17]. The following are some of the control mechanisms discussed in the literature.

Distributed Control Systems proved to be fast and rigid through a series of homogenous and scalable experiments using modular robots [18].

Magnetic Control Systems have an independent controlling mechanism for each individual moving unit. Lee *et al.* introduced self-levitating objects called “ZeroNs”. ZeroNs use magnetic control systems to control the interactive movements of the robots. Robots transfer their positions by

synchronizing the 3D shapes with an optical tracking and display system and use fixed magnets in the objects [19].

Pneumatically Actuated Soft Composite Materials are used for building and controlling the interfaces in charge of changing the shape formation. Composite multi-layer materials use sensing data to produce an active shape assembly [20, 21]. While intelligent self-levitating robots use local sensing only to coordinate their movements, composite-material systems can automatically generate low-level rules to enable independent climbing robots to produce the user-specified construction [3, 22].

Pin-Based Shape Displays control moving blocks (called “Kinetic Blocks”) with an array of vertically actuated pins. The blocks are moved, and the underlying pins sense the blocks’ poses. Blocks can convert pins movements from moving only vertically to other types of movements such as rotation or moving horizontally. The different types of movements are called degrees of freedom. This approach can move and control objects stacked on top of each other and is thus able to perform self-reconfiguration. This kinetic display gives a physical form to digital information. It also provides shape displays with the ability to assemble and disassemble, and permits otherwise-inaccessible forms to be created [23, 24].

Admittance Control to Quadrocopters was developed by Augugliaro and D’Andrea to provide robotic physical interaction. Knowing the object’s position coordinates, consistent behaviors, and the current external force estimations allows the user to control the object’s motion [10].

Gestural Input Recompose Systems employ gestural input for direct functional manipulation [25]. “Floatio” is an example of the implementation of a hand-over mechanism, developed in combination with a floating field and a pointer apparatus [26].

Freehand Gesture Control is, to the best of our knowledge, the most recently considered controlling mechanism. Ren and O’Neill tried to simplify the process of controlling flying drones by selecting them with a freehand gesture. This controller is considered to be a direct human-material interaction method, without the use of other external supportive devices [27]. The user can simply wave their hand to select all or part of the flying robots, modify their trajectories, assign moving directions, or adjust the robots’ degrees of freedom [28].

Force Curves

The current paper will extend the concept of physical programming to incorporate attraction and repulsion forces between physical objects. These attraction and repulsion forces are modelled on intermolecular relations and force curves to effect self-organization.

Thermally induced forces will be used as an example. The application of a source of heat will cause molecules to vibrate. The vibrating molecules will affect the direction and speed of their neighboring molecules. The effect of one vibrating molecule upon its neighbors depends upon the material properties, which we embody in “force curves”, a graphical representation of the application of force on an object. These molecular force curves will be physically demonstrated using programmable drones (BitDrones) which can adjust their planned geometry by changing their angular motion [29].

Fairness measures and computational techniques for force curves have been discussed by Leithinger and Ishii, who introduced superior quality curves and surfaces based on minimizing the variation of curvature [23]. The current paper will introduce and evaluate a faster curve computational technique using bottom-up programming.

3D Physical Visualization

3D physical visualization shows digital information using physical structures, which permits physical human-computer collaboration. The user has a tangible user interface to design physical constructions [30, 31].

As an example, Jansen *et al.* showed how a flying drone can demonstrate real molecular interactions (attractions and repulsions) to prove that physical demonstration of science makes knowledge more retrievable [32]. Since describing the unseen world is not an easy task, involving the use of special senses like touching and sensing in the educational process proved to help in knowledge retrieval and recall.

Nozaki discussed 3D physical visualisation as a means of public service using physical displays or projectors, showing that these displays were able to remain stable in a 3D space, which permits the drones to fly closer to people [10, 33].

Data Physicalizing is a new term used for shape-changing robotic displays that use computer-aided physical data representation. Recent advances in 3D physical visualization include digital fabrication and actuated tangible interfaces [34].

CONTRIBUTION AND JUSTIFICATION

Physical Objects Control Systems

Researchers have discussed the difficulty and complexity of controlling physical objects for a long time. Research experiments have suggested conceptual solutions, such as Programmable Matter [1, 2], Radical Atoms [35], or Claytronics [6].

Programming Physical Structures

Programming physical structures is not an easy task. The current paper will introduce an innovative use of PM via programming forms of matter that can control themselves. This is called self-reconfiguration and can eliminate excessive programming.

Distributed Computational Systems

One popular method of controlling physical objects is through distributed computational systems. This solution consists of synchronous mobile computational entities, where the pattern formation class controls the structures' motion. The class can move the objects in a rotational, scaling, or reflective fashion, until they form the desired pattern [36].

In the world of inter-disciplinary PM, distributed computational systems are not sufficient to change the structures' physical features, shapes, and appearance. This insufficiency is because most current systems are based on streaming sensors' data or user input, which adds an extra layer of complexity to distributed computations.

Feature Adjustment

The complexity of programming individual drones has always been the biggest challenge in managing larger numbers of drones. Researchers tried to solve the programming complexity by adjusting the drones' mechanical and electronic design features [37]. Designing more economic and easily assembled structures (e.g., drones) was one of the researchers' main goals [7]. Feature adjustment and control enabled the programming of a relatively large number of robots that could form the desired physical 3D pattern simply by charging them and turning them on.

Bottom-Up Programming

Bottom-up programming proved to scale better, especially for elastic forms of matter. It also proved to be simpler to program as will be shown later in the implementation section of the current paper. This programming simplicity will allow the developers to program an overarching construction simulation.

For example, in programming a simulation of a stretching material (e.g., a rubber band), it would be difficult to program in a top-down fashion because it requires lots of layered programming in separate sections. With bottom-up programming, users can simply assign the elasticity feature to 20 drones, for instance, and the drones will immediately simulate the rubber band stretching behavior.

The material properties and features must be pre-programmed first. Then, they are fed into the physical structures controlling system in order to apply the material feature simulation (e.g., elasticity) in a 3D physical construction.

Force Curves

Defining the external effecting forces on static or moving objects can help to understand the moving objects better, and their effects on each other. Force curves help in predicting the moving objects'

directions and speeds with almost zero friction rate. Friction rate is the motion resistance force with opposite direction to the object, which usually slows down the object's speed [38, 39].

Self-Reconfiguration

Self-reconfiguration is a physical structure governing principle. It is a necessary principle to avoid the individual programming of each drone or computational unit. It is desirable and a lot simpler to program different properties (e.g., rubber elasticity or cement rigidity), so that, by applying them, all structures organize their positions and behaviors accordingly.

Self-organizing mechanisms are implemented in the proposed solution as self-reconfigurable mid-air flying drones. The drones in the experiment demonstrated in the current paper control themselves by following a dominant drone, which is selected with a hand gesture. The user assigns the desired 3D visualization model, after which the drones perform the simulation behavior.

The self-reconfiguration principle has proved to be efficient according to Rubenstein *et al.* [40]. Researchers in [40] implemented a two-dimensional shaping of a thousand-robot swarm. The main idea is to provide the system with shape formation algorithms. Physical units or structures will execute shape formation algorithms once the user activates them. The current paper will address the main challenges to self-reconfiguration, such as scalability and algorithm complexity.

IMPLEMENTATION

System Overview

The aim of this side implementation is to develop an interactive demonstration of the attraction-repulsion force curves to extend the concept of programmable matter, or simply, physical programming. For demonstration, the implementation uses self-reconfigurable mid-air flying programmable drones (BitDrones) that can control themselves through distributed computational systems, where the pattern formation class controls the structures' motion. A dominant drone will be programmed to be followed by all other drones. The dominant node is selected and controlled with a hand gesture for smooth interaction with the drones via the use of MRTK-Unity object manipulator script.

This implementation follows a bottom-up programming method for physical structures using Unity 3D as a programming platform. This programming method is proposed as a faster curve computational technique. The efficiency of bottom-up programming to control physical structures will be verified through fast and successful adjustments to the molecules force curves. To achieve this adjustment successfully in unity 3D with proper interact ability in HoloLens, force curves will be defined for two parameters, attraction and repulsion, between physical molecules. Considering only those two parameters, this experiment will investigate the possibility of constructing 3D behavior simulations for different forms of matter.

Force Curves

The relationship between the two force curves is explained in Figure 1. The relationship line is affected by an external force on the Y axis causing an acceleration on the X axis. The external force and the acceleration will be reflected on the drones' planned geometry by changing their angular motion to mimic the elasticity motion. This elasticity curve (attraction and repulsion) is visualized on Microsoft HoloLens.

Figure 1. Attraction-Repulsion Force Curves

A force directed graph will be explained to fully understand the attraction and repulsion behavior. Initially, drones' positions will be identified in equal distances from each other in such a way that sustains neutral floating in an equilibrium state, Figure 2 and Figure 3. Then, an external force will be assigned to certain nodes to enact the attraction or repulsion motion simulation.

Figure 2. Drone Positions Identified with Equal Distances and Visualized Through HoloLens

Figure 2. Drone positions identified with equal distances at UnityEngine

The nodes and their edges will move accordingly as a response to the external force effect on them. To simulate the repulsion effect, the edges between the nodes become longer. In the contrary, to simulate the attraction, the edges become shorter. Once this algorithm is programmed, it is exported from Unity 3D to the HoloLens via a Mixed Reality toolkit (MRTK-Unity), which is used for cross-platform programming, and the UnityEngine library. This architecture is depicted on Figure 4. Holographic Remoting is used to wirelessly connect the developed molecular force curve program, developed on Unity 3D, with the Microsoft HoloLens.

Figure 4. Architecture Overview of the Developed System

MS HoloLens and BitDrones Programming

In MS HoloLens, the following Unity 3D settings, Figure 5, are fixed for proper connection with the main camera.

Figure 5. SEQ Figure * ARABIC 5 Unity 3D settings for camera connection

Code 1 represents the drones initialization stage by assigning their floating percentage in relation to gravity.


```
// Drones initialization

void Start () {

    rigid = GetComponent<Rigidbody>();

}

}
```

Code 2 represents the two force curves, attraction and repulsion, induced via an external force. Code 3 represents the dominant drone identification system. The main camera will take the hand gesture coordinates and feed them into the system.

```
private void Node ()
{
    //External force causing repulsion
    foreach (Node i in nodes.Values)
    {
        i.force Vector.zero;
        foreach (Node j in nodes.Values)
        {
            if (i.id == j.id) continue;
            Vector dis= i.transform.position - j.transform.position;
            i.force += ((dis.normalized/10)/(dis.magnitude * dis.magnitude)*c)/10000;
        }
    }
}
```

```
void FixedUpdate ()
{
    ControlSignal signal = new ControlSignal();

    signal.Throttle = Input.GetAxis("LeftY");
    signal.Rudder = Input.GetAxis("LeftX");
}
```

As per the second code snippet, Code 2, showing the private function named Node, programming started at the node level to assign attraction and repulsion force curves. Since nodes are the smallest part of the architecture, this is considered a bottom-up programming method. As such, the function will control the drone's movements, not the class identification. Furthermore, any adjustments to the force curves will be done at the node level, not the class upper level.

Technical and Functional Evaluation

For a seamless interaction with the BitDrones, effective communication across Unity 3D and MS HoloLens platforms must be ensured. Instant response by the dominant drone to the hand gesture was evaluated for its latency. The time between the thrust of a hand gesture and the dominant BitDrone's response was computed to be 17ms. The time between the dominant BitDrone movement and the following BitDrones to follow was also computed to be around 9ms. This latency examination was repeated 30 times and average latency readings were calculated and reported in this section. This is a widely acceptable range of latency in such applications.

While only 7 BitDrones were involved in this experiment, it is undoubtedly scalable to larger numbers of drones following the adopted bottom-up programming. This programming method has proved to be less complex in terms of implemented algorithm and more efficient to making changes or adjustments, easier to code, and hence makes a more sustainable and maintainable system.

Accuracy was also tested in terms of drones' deviation ratio from the proper trajectory. The elasticity demonstration of the force curves was accurately represented with a deviation ratio of 2.5%, which is considered as a failure ratio of the drones to follow the correct path.

TOOLS

BitDrones

For a realistic user interface, BitDrones will be used as a real-world object display medium. BitDrones are interactive construction platforms, used to form tangible building blocks [2]. BitDrones support the formation of shapes and structures in a 3D visualization pattern. They provide physical interaction with the user by self-levitating to the user's vision level [3].

HoloLens

The HoloLens is the only functional Augmented Reality System (ARS) developed by Microsoft (MS) [27, 41]. It provides control and management capabilities over physical drones.

Unity 3D Engine

The Unity 3D Engine [42] is a software used to program and model the 3D visualization process. It is used because it works effectively with the HoloLens. The Unity 3D Engine allows programmers to prototype their architectures easily by providing the basic physics and features needed for the modelling procedure.

CONCLUSION

Programming large numbers of drones effectively is prohibitively hard. The self-reconfiguration mechanism has proved to be a far better programming methodology. Bottom-up programming has also proved to be effective at solving both physical programming complexity, and individual drone design, management, and control.

This paper represents a successful implementation of an interactive 3D physical simulation of the attraction and repulsion forces via physical programming. This physical demonstration has successfully incorporated a self-reconfigurable mid-air flying programmable drones.

Furthermore, a programming methodology that focuses on the bottom level was adopted. The bottom-up programming style has proved to be more efficient in many ways, including changeability, maintainability, and scalability. The implementation was tested mainly

A minimum latency was reported by the experiment as well as the trajectory deviation ratio. The readings were marginal which leads to a conclusion of a successful implementation and development of an interactive force curves setting of BitDrones through Unity 3D.

FUTURE WORK

Investigating the possibility of programming inter-matter or inter-molecular relationships is suggested as a replacement for the individual drone field. This development has the potential to divide the drones into two separate constructions that can interact with each other, but never merge.

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